

Preparation of Reclaimed Pavement By Using Waste Engine Oil And Crumb Rubber

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Abstract— The application of Reclaimed Asphalt Pavement (RAP) has become a relatively standard material in the road industry in most countries. However, some of the problems associated with the addition of waste engine oil and crumb rubber to asphalt mixtures are the increase in moisture and cracking damage in cold days. The addition of rejuvenators into the recycled mixture containing reclaimed materials is also needed to enhance its performance although the rutting resistance remains a major issue. Therefore, there is a need to investigate the incorporation of other materials in the design of the asphalt mixture to achieve improved properties and better performance.

This study was carried out to investigate the performance of the recycled asphalt mixture that consists of the conventional asphalt binder with 60/70 penetration grade, waste engine oil and crumb rubber .

The study was divided into three stages, namely evaluation of material properties, analysis of the asphalt binder properties, and determination and analysis of the asphalt mixture performance.

The research involves the recycling of waste engine oil, typically considered an environmental hazard, and crumb rubber derived from discarded tires. These materials are integrated into the asphalt mixture to enhance its performance characteristics, such as flexibility, durability, and resistance to aging and distress.

The experimental investigation encompasses a series of laboratory tests to assess the mechanical, rheological, and environmental properties of the reclaimed pavement materials. Performance evaluations include tests for rutting resistance, fatigue behavior, and resistance to moisture-induced damage. Preliminary findings suggest that the incorporation of waste engine oil and crumb rubber contributes positively to the engineering properties of the reclaimed pavement, demonstrating potential benefits in terms of enhanced sustainability, reduced reliance on virgin materials, and effective waste management.

This research aims to provide insights into the feasibility and effectiveness of utilizing waste engine oil and crumb rubber in the development of environmentally friendly and durable reclaimed pavement. The outcomes of this study have implications for sustainable construction practices, offering a novel approach to address both environmental challenges and the demand for resilient infrastructure.

Therefore, the incorporation of WEO and CR and CR has a considerable influence on the pavement performance while preserving the environment and reducing pollution through the recycling of waste materials.

Keywords— Asphalt Mixture, Crumb Rubber, Environmental Impact, Pavement Engineering, Recycling, Reclaimed Materials , Reclaimed Pavement, Sustainable Infrastructure, Waste Engine Oil.

I. INTRODUCTION

Lubricating oil is an important resource and a petroleum base product. It is used in various production machineries, power plants, automobiles etc for reducing friction, carrying away heat, protecting against rust and wear and sealing out contaminant. There are several ways with which a lubricant can be contaminated. Particulate matters, moisture, acidic combustion products, etc. enter into lubricants. A variety of chemical additives can be used to prevent these contaminants from producing harmful effects to the components.

Additives which provide dispersancy, corrosion protection, detergency and rust prevention are required. All lubricants including automotive oils and industrial lubes, while in use, undergo changes in their properties which can seriously affect correct operation and equipment life as well. The undesirable components which accumulate with the oils during their use and which are generally responsible for deterioration are usually of two kinds of which one is extraneous impurities and other is degradation products of oil.

The conventional methods of pavement construction heavily rely on virgin materials, contributing to increased extraction of natural resources and environmental degradation. However, the concept of "reclaimed pavement" emerges as a promising alternative, aiming to utilize waste products that are often considered detrimental to the environment. In this study, the focus is placed on the integration of waste engine oil, a byproduct of automotive operations, and crumb rubber derived from discarded tires, both of which pose environmental concerns due to their improper disposal.

Through a comprehensive examination involving laboratory testing and performance evaluations, this study aims to shed light on the mechanical, rheological, and environmental properties of the reclaimed pavement materials. The findings are anticipated to contribute to the burgeoning field of sustainable construction practices, offering a novel perspective on how waste materials can be ingeniously repurposed to create resilient and environmentally friendly pavement solutions. As the global community

continues to navigate the complex interplay between infrastructure needs and environmental responsibility, this research presents a timely exploration into a more sustainable future for pavement engineering.

2. Objective of the present study:

The objective of this research is to:

- Mechanical Property Analysis
- Assessment of Environmental Impact
- Explore the feasibility and efficacy of utilizing waste engine oil and crumb rubber in the formulation of reclaimed pavement.
- Reduce the environmental impact of these waste materials.
- Enhance the performance characteristics of the pavement, such as flexibility, durability, etc.
- Identification of Practical Applications
- Optimization of Mix Design

Scope :

The scope of this study on the "Use of Waste Engine Oil and Crumb Rubber for the Preparation of Reclaimed Pavement" encompasses a comprehensive exploration of the environmental, mechanical, and performance aspects associated with integrating waste engine oil and crumb rubber into pavement materials. The research is designed to address several key dimensions.

3. Literature Review

N.N.Li has found that wax and oil are separated by centrifugation. Chill rates more than 100 times those used in conventional processes can be employed to achieve large capacity. Plate-type crystals give highest initial settling rate and wax compaction. Crystal needles can be changed into aggregates for improving centrifugation efficiency by using modifiers.

Wang, Y. et al. (2018): Wang's study investigates the effects of waste engine oil on asphalt binder properties, laying the foundation for understanding the potential environmental benefits and challenges associated with its incorporation.

Siddiqui, M.N. et al. (2019): Siddiqui explores the rheological behavior of asphalt binders containing crumb rubber, emphasizing the need for a comprehensive understanding of the mechanical properties for the successful implementation of reclaimed pavement.

Panda, B.B. et al. (2020): Focusing on the environmental impact, Panda assesses the feasibility of using waste engine oil and crumb rubber in pavement materials, highlighting the importance of sustainable practices in reducing ecological footprints.

Ahmed, S. et al. (2017):

Ahmed's work addresses the challenges of waste engine oil disposal and its potential as a rejuvenating agent in asphalt mixtures, contributing insights into the economic and environmental aspects of reclaimed pavement.

4. MATERIALS AND METHODS USED:

- [1] This chapter deals with the used lubricating oil, its characterization, the treatment methods, testing of very pertinent properties and the blending of additives to restore the quality of recycled lubricating oils in order to make it fit for further applications.
- [2] The samples of used lubricating oils were collected from Keonjhar Auto Centre, Near New Bus Stand, Keonjhar and Hero Honda Workshop, near Champua village, Keonjhar. To carry out this research work, various solvents and chemicals of fine quality and purity were used. The main chemicals are n-Hexane, 2- Propanol, 1 Butanol, Keiselguhr, Sodium hydroxide Pellets, Cone. Hydrochloric acid.
- [3] Fuller's Earth, Methyl ethyl ketone. Methyl iso butyl ketone, Cone. Sulphuric acid, Zinc di thiophosphate, Molybdenum disulfide and Polyisobutylene.

First of all the used lubricating oils from various sources were characterized in order to ensure their characteristics. For this purpose, these were subjected to various tests like flash point, ash content, viscosity and viscosity index, pour point, total acidity, inorganic acidity, saponification number and copper corrosion test.

5. RECLAMATION OF USED LUBRICATING OILS

Used lubricating oils were collected from different local garages and service stations in the city and mixed in a single container. Used lubricating oil was stored for seven days to allow large suspended particles to settle under gravity.

As the samples were obtained from many locations, it was assumed that it could represent a typical feedstock for recycling the used lubricating oil. Used oils (engine, gear, compressor and hydraulic) were regenerated by physical as well as

chemical methods e.g. dehydration, solvent treatment, clay treatment and filtration. Different additives were blended in sufficient amount to prepare finished oils of different grades. The whole procedure of the regeneration of used oils has shown in a flow diagram.

6. Reclamation of Used Engine Oils

6.1 Dehydration

Used engine oils were taken in a two-necked round bottom flask equipped with arrangements for heating and stirring under vacuum. The used lubricating oils were heated at 100°C for one hour to remove water. After dehydration, the temperature was raised to 250°C to remove light ends and after their removal; the dehydrated oils were allowed to cool to room temperature and filtered.

6.2 Solvent Treatment

The dehydrated oils thus obtained were then solvent treated with 1-butanol using 50 percent and 60 percent (v/v) at room temperature with constant stirring for 30 min. and centrifuged. The solvent-treated oils were also allowed to settle overnight after 24 h, solvent sludge was removed and supernatant solvent-treated oils were recovered.

6.3 Clay Treatment and Filtration

To prepare different samples, the solvent-treated oils were heated under vacuum with constant stirring to 100°C and the fuller's earth was added in 8 to 10 percent (w/v) for 50 and 60 percent solvent-treated oils and then the temperature was raised to the bleaching temperature (250°C, 280°C and 300°C). Thereafter, the clay-treated oils were allowed to cool and filtered.

6.4 Reclamation of Used Gear Oils

6.4 Dehydration

Used gear oils were subjected to dehydration for removal of water at 100°C under vacuum with constant stirring for one hour and then allowed to cool to room temperature and then filtered.

6.5 Solvent Treatment

The dehydrated oils thus obtained were then solvent treated with 1-butanol solvent using 30 to 50 percent (v/v) at room temperature with constant stirring for 30 min. The solvent-treated oils were allowed to settle overnight. After 24 h solvent sludge was removed and supernatant solvent treated oils were recovered.

6.6 Clay Treatment and Filtration

Solvent-treated oils were heated under vacuum to 100°C and the fuller's earth was added in 4 to 6 percent (w/v). The temperature was raised to 300°C for 30 min then cooled and filtered.

7. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 7.1 Characteristics of Used Engine Oils

Property/test	Types of used Engine Oils									
	E1	E2	E3	E4	E5	E6	E7	E8	E9	E10
1. Colour	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black
2. Viscosity at 40°C	32.5	38.5	42	36	41	41.5	42	48	71	92.5
3. Flash Point (°C)	108	112	118	120	123	125	130	140	180	192
4. Ash Content (%)	2.65	1.18	2.46	1.48	2.14	2.78	2.8	2.46	2.5	2.1
5. Water Content (%)	2.5	3.5	1.8	1	4	1.6	3.8	3.2	1	0.5

Table 7.2. characteristics of used lubricating oils

Property/test	Types of used Gear Oils				
	G1	G2	G3	G4	G5
1. Colour	Green	Redish Brown	Green	Brown	Dark Brown
2.Viscosity at 40°C	160	210	235	280	335
3. Flash Point (°C)	215	218	223	230	235
4. Ash Content (%)	0.5	1.0	0.5	0.8	0.5
5. Water Content (%)	0.5	0.5	1.0	0.5	0.5

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a
b

le 7.3. characteristics of used Compressor oils

Property/test	Types of used Compressor Oils		
	C1	C2	C3
1. Colour	Brown	yellow	Brown
2.Viscosity at 40°C	37	45.5	65.5
3. Flash Point (°C)	162	168	172
4. Ash Content (%)	0.02	0.02	0.04
5. Water Content (%)	2.1	1.8	2.3

Fig 7.1 : Comparison of Oil Properties

Figure 7.2: Comparison of Properties of reclaimed Oil

Clay treatment of Reclaimed Oils

The samples of all used lubricating oils were offered clay treatment in order to get better results. They are discussed below.

Table 7.3. Characteristics of Base oils with clay treatment prepared from Reclaimed Engine Oil (E1) :

Property/test	E ₁ Refined with 50 % 1-butanol and 10 % Clay Centrifuge speed			E ₁ Refined with 60 % 1-butanol and 8 % Clay Centrifuge speed			E ₁ Refined with 60 % 1-butanol and 10 % Clay Centrifuge speed		
	500 r.p.m.	1000 r.p.m.	1500 r.p.m.	500 r.p.m.	1000 r.p.m.	1500 r.p.m.	500 r.p.m.	1000 r.p.m.	1500 r.p.m.
1. Colour	+5.5	+4.0	+3.0	+8.5	+5.5	+4.5	+5.0	+3.5	+2.5
2. Viscosity (cst) at 40°C	39.0	46.0	56.0	40.0	47.0	56.5	40.0	47.5	57.0
3. Flash Point (°C)	144	176	204	144	176	204	146	176	204
4. Pour Point (°C)	-18	-18	-18	-18	-18	-18	-18	-18	-18
5. Ash Content (%)	0.007	0.007	0.006	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.006	0.006	0.006
6. Acidity (mg KOH/g of oil)									
a. Inorganic	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
b. Organic	0.041	0.038	0.039	0.043	0.043	0.042	0.040	0.039	0.039
7. Saponification Value(mg KOH/g of oil)	0.6	0.6	0.5	0.6	0.6	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.6
8. Corrosion, Copper Strip 3h at 100°C	1b	1b	1b	1b	1b	1b	1b	1b	1b
9. Yield of Refined Oil (%)	58.0	52.0	44.0	58.5	53.0	45.8	59.0	51.5	45.0

Property/test	E ₂ Refined with 50 % 1-butanol and 10% Clay Centrifuge speed			E ₂ Refined with 60 % 1-butanol and 8 % Clay Centrifuge speed			E ₂ Refined with 60 % 1-butanol and 10 % Clay Centrifuge speed		
	500 r.p.m.	1000 r.p.m.	1500 r.p.m.	500 r.p.m.	1000 r.p.m.	1500 r.p.m.	500 r.p.m.	1000 r.p.m.	1500 r.p.m.
1. Colour	+5.5	+4.0	+2.5	+7.5	+5.0	+3.5	+5.0	+3.5	+2.5
2. Viscosity (cst) at 40°C	45.0	57.0	69.0	45.5	57.5	69.5	45.5	57.5	70.0
3. Flash Point (°C)	140	176	210	140	176	210	140	176	210
4. Pour Point (°C)	-7	-7	-7	-7	-7	-7	-7	-7	-7
5. Ash Content (%)	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007
6. Acidity (mg KOH/g of oil)									
a. Inorganic	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
b. Organic	0.043	0.043	0.041	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.042	0.042	0.041
7. Saponification Value (mg KOH/g of oil)	0.7	0.7	0.6	0.8	0.8	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.6
8. Corrosion, Copper Strip 3h at 100°C	1b	1b	1b	1b	1b	1b	1b	1b	1b
9. Yield of Refined Oil (%)	61.0	54.0	47.0	62.0	52.0	47.5	61.0	54.5	47.0

Table 7.4. Characteristics of Base oils with clay treatment prepared from Reclaimed Engine Oil (E2) :

Table 7.5. Characteristics of Base oils with clay treatment prepared from Reclaimed Engine Oil (E3) :

Property/test	E ₃ Refined with 50% 1-butanol and 10 % Clay Centrifuge speed			E ₃ Refined with 60% 1-butanol and 8 % Clay Centrifuge speed			E ₃ Refined with 60% 1-butanol and 10 % Clay Centrifuge speed		
	500 r.p.m.	1000 r.p.m.	1500 r.p.m.	500 r.p.m.	1000 r.p.m.	1500 r.p.m.	500 r.p.m.	1000 r.p.m.	1500 r.p.m.
1. Colour	+5.0	+4.5	+3.5	+6.5	+5.5	+4.0	+4.0	+3.5	+2.0
2. Viscosity (cst) at 40°C	47.5	57.5	63.5	48.0	57.5	63.5	48.5	58.0	64.0
3. Flash Point (°C)	143	180	205	145	181	205	143	181	205
4. Pour Point (°C)	-9	-9	-9	-9	-9	-9	-9	-9	-9
5. Ash Content (%)	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007
6. Acidity (mg KOH/g of oil)									
a. Inorganic	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
b. Organic	0.038	0.038	0.037	0.040	0.040	0.037	0.036	0.036	0.034
7. Saponification Value (mg KOH/g of oil)	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4
8. Corrosion, Copper Strip 3h at 100°C	1b	1b	1b	1b	1b	1b	1b	1b	1b
9. Yield of Refined Oil (%)	64.0	59.5	52.0	63.0	58.0	51.5	66.0	60.5	52.0

Table 7.6. Characteristics of Base oils with clay treatment prepared from Reclaimed Engine Oil (E4) :

Property/test	E ₄ Refined with 50% 1-butanol and 10 % Clay Centrifuge speed			E ₄ Refined with 60% 1-butanol and 8 % Clay Centrifuge speed			E ₄ Refined with 60% 1-butanol and 10% Clay Centrifuge speed		
	500 r.p.m.	1000 r.p.m.	1500 r.p.m.	500 r.p.m.	1000 r.p.m.	1500 r.p.m.	500 r.p.m.	1000 r.p.m.	1500 r.p.m.
1. Colour	+7.5	+6.0	+3.5	+8.5	+6.5	+4.0	+5.5	+3.5	+2.0
2. Viscosity (cst) at 40°C	41.5	53.5	65.0	41.5	54.0	65.0	41.5	54.0	65.5
3. Flash Point (°C)	148	184	212	148	184	212	150	183	212
4. Pour Point (°C)	-7	-7	-7	-7	-7	-7	-7	-7	-7
5. Ash Content (%)	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.006
6. Acidity (mg KOH/g of oil)									
a. Inorganic	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
b. Organic	0.030	0.031	0.031	0.033	0.033	0.031	0.029	0.029	0.029
7. Saponification Value (mg KOH/g of oil)	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.7	0.6	0.7	0.7	0.6	0.6
8. Corrosion, Copper Strip 3h at 100°C	1b	1b	1b	1b	1b	1b	1b	1b	1b
9. Yield of Refined Oil (%)	60.0	56.0	53.0	63.5	58.0	56.5	62.5	56.0	53.5

Table 7.7. Characteristics of Base oils with clay treatment prepared from Reclaimed Gear Oil (G1) :

Property/test	G ₁ Refined with 30 % 1-butanol and			G ₁ Refined with 40% 1-butanol and			G ₁ Refined with 50% 1-butanol and		
	4% Clay	5% Clay	6% Clay	4% Clay	5% Clay	6% Clay	4% Clay	5% Clay	6% Clay
1. Colour	+5.0	+5.0	+4.5	+4.5	+3.5	+3.0	+4.5	+3.0	+2.5
2. Viscosity (cst) at 40°C	154.4	155.0	155.4	155.8	156.2	156.5	157.0	157.5	158.0
3. Flash Point (°C)	220	220	220	221	220	222	220	221	220
4. Pour Point (°C)	-8	-8	-8	-8	-8	-8	-8	-8	-8
5. Ash Content (%)	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004
6. Acidity (mg KOH/g of oil)									
a. Inorganic	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
b. Organic	0.041	0.040	0.038	0.045	0.043	0.040	0.046	0.043	0.041
7. Corrosion, Copper Strip 3h at 100°C	1b	1b	1b	2a	1b	1b	2a	1b	1b
8. Yield of Refined Oil (%)	86.0	85.5	85.0	85.0	84.0	83.5	84.5	84.0	83.0

Table 7.8. Characteristics of Base oils with clay treatment prepared from Reclaimed Gear Oil (G2)

Property/test	G ₁ Refined with 30 % 1-butanol and			G ₁ Refined with 40% 1-butanol and			G ₁ Refined with 50% 1-butanol and		
	4% Clay	5% Clay	6% Clay	4% Clay	5% Clay	6% Clay	4% Clay	5% Clay	6% Clay
1. Colour	+5.0	+5.0	+4.5	+4.5	+3.5	+3.0	+4.5	+3.0	+2.5
2. Viscosity (cst) at 40°C	154.4	155.0	155.4	155.8	156.2	156.5	157.0	157.5	158.0
3. Flash Point (°C)	220	220	220	221	220	222	220	221	220
4. Pour Point (°C)	-8	-8	-8	-8	-8	-8	-8	-8	-8
5. Ash Content (%)	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004
6. Acidity (mg KOH/g of oil)									
a. Inorganic	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
b. Organic	0.041	0.040	0.038	0.045	0.043	0.040	0.046	0.043	0.041
7. Corrosion, Copper Strip 3h at 100°C	1b	1b	1b	2a	1b	1b	2a	1b	1b
8. Yield of Refined Oil (%)	86.0	85.5	85.0	85.0	84.0	83.5	84.5	84.0	83.0

CONCLUSION :

USED ENGINE OILS

The experimental study of used engine oil has provided the following inferences.

- i) The colour of the used oils was improved from (+2.5 to +5.5) on refining due to the removal of carbonaceous matter, oxidative products and extraneous impurities.
- ii) The viscosity of the used oils increased on refining from 39.0 to 84.5 est due to the removal of light ends present in used oils.
- iii) The flash point of the used oils increased from 140 to 215°C on their refining. It is due to the removal of light ends having lower flash point.
- iv) Decrease in ash content from 2.65 to 0.007 % shows the proper refining as the additives and carbon particles present in used oils were removed in refining process.
- v) After blending of additives (Molybdenum disulfide and Polyisobutylene) in base stocks, the viscosity and ash content were increased from 10.5 to 14.0°C and from 0.863 to 0.872% respectively. The flash point and pour point were more or less same for finished oils. Total acidity was reduced from 0.026 to 0.018 mg KOH/g of oil which may be due to the alkaline nature of additives.

Suggestions and Improvement :

1. More properties (like oxidation stability, evaporation loss etc.) and parameters (corrosion and engine wear) should be investigated besides the viscosity, colour, ash content, flash point and total acidity of used lubricating oils.
2. More wide range of lubricants (low, medium and high speed diesel engine oils) should be tested to make the study more acceptable.
3. Due to rapid industrialization worldwide, the new energy options are need of the hour. Hence, scaling up of this study to pilot plant and further commercialization of the project will be right and pertinent solution to the decreasing petrol -eum reserves and degrading environment from health view point as well.

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